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Online Campus Recruitment System

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Abstract

The aim of this paper was to investigate the effective ways to maximize the role of recruitment agencies in Raipur. Bhilai was chosen as a location of this study. This qualitative study involved 7 informants from 3 categories: the recruitment agency operators, the employers, and the job applicants. This study reviews the integration issues in e-recruiting and presents an e-recruiting integration decision model. This project has a very wide scope this project contains most important part i.e. Displaying the personal and academics information of student and company. In order to fulfill its objectives, mission and various activities, it is necessary to ensure the quality and number of employees also in the public administration. As stated earlier, recruitment refers to the process of identifying and attracting job seekers so as to build a pool of qualified job

applicants. The process comprises of five interrelated stages: (i) planning, (ii) strategy development, (iii) searching, (iv) screening, and (v) Evaluation and control. The ideal recruitment program is the one that attracts a relatively large number of qualified applicants who will survive the screening process and accept positions with the organization when offered.

Key words: Recruitment process; public administration; effectivity in the recruitment process.

Introduction

The campus recruitment system is a project which provides a bridge between Student and Campus Recruitment Department. With the help of this system. The project is beneficial for college students, various companies visiting the campus for recruitment and even the college placement officer.

The system handles student as well as company data and efficiently displays all this data to respective sides. The objective of these websites is to serve as a common meeting ground for jobseekers and employers, both locally and globally, where the candidates find their dream jobs and recruiters find the right candidate to fulfill their needs. This project is specifically designed for those who seek the most demanding and challenging positions in their chosen field, with the most dynamic employers.

1.1 Objective

The major objective of Campus Recruitment System is to identify the talented and qualified professionals before they complete their education. It provides employment opportunities to the students who are perusing or in the final stage of completing the course. This process reduces the time for an industry to pick the candidates according to their need. It is a cumbersome activity and hence majority of the companies find it difficult to trace the right talent. Many students do not understand the importance of placement training that is being imparted, whether it is aptitude training or soft skills. They show the least interest in this due to various factors projects, assignments or more of activities loaded by the colleges as part of their curriculum thinking that it is not useful. It is the responsibility of the companies training on placement to make the students equipped on all aspects of career development along with creating a very good impact in them which makes them feel every minute they spend in the placement training session is worth being there and will help them in getting placed in their dream companies.

1.2 Literature review

Recruitment is one of the major functions of HRM. It helps the manager to attract and select best candidates for the organization. Parry & Wilson (2009) stated that "recruitment includes those practices and activities carried out by the organization with the primary purpose of identifying and attracting potential employees". As success of service sector as in case of civil aviation industry depends upon the human capital, recruitment & selection of the right people into the service business is crucial

to achieve organizational success (Zheng, 2009). Raymond J. Stone (2005) in the fifth edition of his book Human Resource Management defines recruitment as the process of 'seeking and attracting a pool of applicants from which qualified candidates for job vacancies within an organization can be selected.' According to Edwin B. Flippo, "Recruitment is the process of searching the candidates for employment and stimulating them to apply for jobs in the organization". (1979) Recruitment is an activity that links the employers and the job seekers. So we can say that recruitment is a process of finding and attracting capable applicants for 19 employment. The process begins when new recruits are sought and ends when their applications are submitted. The result is a pool of applications from which new employees are selected. In simple terms, recruitment is understood as the process of searching for and obtaining applicants for jobs, from among whom the right people can be selected.

1.3 Description of Present System

Present manual system is time consuming. That is if a company or organization needs employees they make an announcement through newspaper. People who are eligible send application to the organization or company. From these applications they are called for interviews or tests. After tests company has to do short listing manually.

1.4 Proposed system

Campus Recruitment is aimed at developing a web-based and central recruitment Process system for the HR Group for a company. Some features of this system will be creating vacancies, storing application data, and Interview process initiation, Scheduling Interviews, Storing Interview results for the applicant and finally hiring of the applicant.

2. Methodology

PHP (Hypertext Preprocessor) is a widely-used open source server-side scripting language for web development and can be embedded into HTML. PHP pages contain HTML with embedded code [23]. PHP offers several advantages:

- PHP runs on different platforms (Windows, Linux, Unix, etc.).
- PHP is compatible with almost all servers used today (Apache, IIS, etc.).
- PHP is free to download from the official PHP resource: www.php.net.

2.1 JavaScript

JavaScript is a client side scripting language designed to add interactivity to HTML pages. A scripting language is a lightweight programming language. It is usually embedded directly into HTML pages. It is an interpreted language which allows the scripts to execute without preliminary compilation. JavaScript can react to events. A JavaScript can be set to execute when something happens, like when a page has finished loading or when a user clicks on an HTML element. JavaScript can read and write HTML elements and can also change it's content and properties. A JavaScript can be used to validate form data before it is submitted to a server. This saves the server from extra processing. A JavaScript can be used to detect the visitor's browser, and depending on the browser, load another page specifically designed for that browser.

2.3 MYSQL

MySQL is a database server is ideal for both small and large applications. It supports standard SQL and compiles on a number of platforms.

2.4 HTML

HTML stands for Hyper Text Markup Language. A markup language is a language that annotates text in a way that is syntactically distinguishable so that the computer can manipulate it. It is a set of markup tags used to describe web pages. The tags are what separate normal text from HTML code. They are the words between the <angle-brackets>. Different tags will perform different functions, like rendering images or tables. It is a combination of words and symbols which give instructions on how the document will be presented. The tags themselves don't appear when you view your page through a browser, but their effects do.

2.5 CSS

CSS stands for Cascading Style Sheets. It is used to control the style and layout of multiple web pages all at once. Styles define how to display HTML elements. CSS overrides the browser's default settings for interpreting how tags should be displayed, letting you use any HTML element indicated by an opening and closing tag to apply style attributes defined either locally or in a style sheet. External Style Sheets can save a lot of work. They are stored in CSS files.

2.6 Feasibility Study

An analysis and evaluation of a proposed project to determine if it

1. Is technically feasible.
2. Is feasible within the estimated cost.
3. Will be profitable.

Feasibility studies are almost always conducted where large sums are at stake.

2.7 Coding

The basic role of this phase is to convert designing into code using the programming language decided in designing phase.

An introductory example,

```
<html>
<head>
<title>Example</title>
</head>
<body>
<?php echo "Hi, I'm a PHP script!"; ?>
</body>
</html>
```

Result

Campus Recruitment System very convenient because in the manual system there are lot of difficulties in conducting and managing a recruitment process.

Conclusion

Students can maintain their information and can update it. Notifications are sent to students about the companies. Students can access previous information about placement. This system has scope of improvement / amendments. In future, sector can communicate with each other online. All currently active

enquires can also be added in the website to view if online. This application can be modified from time to time as per the changing requirement of the user with lesser cost also the backend of the application can be [1]changed as per the storage requirement of the application and to provide more security level features.

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